

Standardization of hybrid rice seed production for Kerala using three-line system of breeding (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Plant growth regulators plays an important role in hybrid rice production mostly by enhancing panicle exertion and grain filling which are the main constraints in rice hybrid seed production in Kerala. The effect of two phytohormones, GA₃(50 ppm and 70 ppm) and brassinosteroid (2 ppm, 6 ppm) at different planting row ratio of female parent to restorer parent (6:2 and 8:2) were studied to identify the suitable combinations for successful hybrid seed production. The results showed that 70 ppm GA₃, 2 ppm brassinosteroid at 6: 2 planting ratio had highest morphological traits, yield, spikelet fertility percentage, number of filled grains and lowest number of unfilled grains. The 8:2 planting ratio (at 70 ppm GA₃ and 2 ppm brassinosteroid) also had highest seed yield due to increased plant population. GA₃ resulted in higher seed set and seed yield by improving the panicle exertion and flag leaf angle. Brassinosteroid played an important role in controlling of seed size and weight. Our findings provide evidence that hybrid rice seed production in Kerala can be enhanced by spraying of 70ppm GA₃ and 2 ppm brassinosteroid at 15-20% heading of tillers and 35-40% panicle emergence. The row ratio of the female parent to the restorer parent can be 8:2 considering the increased seed yield realized.

Keywords : Brassinosteroid, GA₃, Hybrid rice, Planting ratio and Phytohormones.

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the important staple food for about one- third of the world's population. It plays main role in national food security and is a means of livelihood for millions of households in rural areas. Asia accounts for about 90 per cent of world's area and production of rice. India stands first in area but second in production next to China occupying 45.5 million hectares with a production of 99.18 million tons. Compared to other cereals and pulses rice is the major food crop of our nation which accounts 37 percent of the area and 43 percent of total food grain production. However, productivity is much lower than the average productivity of the world (INDIASTAT, 2018). The ever-increasing population and the decrease in arable area led to food shortage and is a serious global problem in this century. Babu *et al.* (2012) reported that area under rice is reducing and productivity is in plateau. Hence, the hybrid rice technology is an option to enhance the productivity of rice.

In Kerala, rice being the staple food, area under rice has been declining due to the fragmentation of land holding and the conversion of wet land under rice cultivation which affects the food security and makes Kerala highly depend on other neighboring states. The actual production of Kerala is around 6 lakh ton which falls far behind the consumption requirement of 40 lakh tons (Abraham, 2019). The Keralites have a high consumer preference for red kernel rice varieties which are more nutritious, its higher in carbohydrate and fiber content than white rice. Kerala is the only state which develops and release red kernelled rice. Hence, the hybrid for Kerala must be red kernelled but so far, no hybrid rice variety has been released from Kerala. One of the reasons is the lack of standardized seed production package for three-line system of breeding. Also, row ratio of parental lines (CMS, to maintainer or restorer lines) plays a vital role in hybrid rice seed production. The suitability of the climate of Kerala for hybrid rice seed production using three-line system also needs validation. External application of phytohormones also contributes to the improved seed set in hybrid production.

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With this background the present study was proposed with the objective of standardization of GA₃, brassinosteroid and optimisation of planting ratio in restorer line (R) and male sterile line (A) to get maximum hybrid seed yield under Kerala condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental material

The female seed parent, CRMS 31A was collected from National Rice Research Institute (NRI), Cuttack, and the male pollen parent, Remya (MO10) was obtained from Rice Research Station (RRS), Mancombu, Kerala; which is restorer parent for CRMS 31A in the three-line breeding programme (Das, 2017). The study comprised of two experiments, Experiment I: Phenological studies in male sterile line (A line), Experiment II: Standardization of GA₃ and brassinosteroid doses for the planting ratio, 6:2 and 8:2 of A and R lines.

Phenological studies in Male Sterile Line (A Line)

Thirty seeds of CMS line were placed in a wet tissue paper in petriplates and well maintained at 37°C. After 21 days, the seedlings were transplanted to pots and watered regularly. The plants were well maintained under controlled condition to reduce the pest and disease incidence. The morphological and floral traits were recorded from ten randomly selected plants per plot at appropriate stages. The following characters were recorded from sterile line according to the procedure given by Virmani(1996).

Tillering stage: number of days from germination to first tiller starts.

Plant height at maturity (cm): from base of the stem to tip of the topmost leaf at 100 DAS.

Total number of productive tillers: Number of tillers from each pot at harvest.

Total number of leaves: Number of leaves was recorded at 100 DAS.

Flag leaf area (cm²): It was measured from length and breadth of leaves at 100 DAS from each plants and mean value was calculated.

Days to panicle primordial initiation: Number of days from germination to panicle primordial initiation. The main tillers were dissected at different days to find the pattern of panicle initiation.

Days to booting: Number of days from germination to booting stage.

Days to panicle emergence: Days from germination to panicle emergence.

Flag leaf angle: It was recorded by measuring the angle between the flag leaf blade midrib and the rachis holding the spikelets within the inflorescence. With the help of a protractor the flag leaf angle was measured by keeping the main panicle axis as basal line, from this basal line to the flag leaf position was measured and expressed in degrees.

Days to anthesis: Number of days from sowing to anthesis was recorded.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed by using statistical package GRAPES from Kerala Agricultural University to analyze the characters.

Standardization GA₃ and brassinosteroid doses for the planting ratio, 6:2 and 8:2 of A and R lines

The second experiment was conducted with A and R line in open field condition at IFSRS, Karamana to standardize the GA₃ and brassinosteroid doses; and to analyze the seed set efficiency in 6:2 and 8:2 planting ratio during hybrid rice seed production programme.

Planting material and planting ratio

The A and R line seeds were germinated on water soaked tissue paper placed in petriplates. The germinated seeds were sown in dapog trays of 60 cm x 30 cm filled with field soil at a spacing of 5 cm between plants. Irrigation was done as required. The major disadvantage in CMS system was low out crossing rate that could be managed by adopting proper planting ratio and by supplementary pollination.

Layout of experiment

Transplanting of 24 days old seedlings of female parent along with 21, 24, 27 days old R line seedlings were done on the 24th day in the main field at a spacing of 20 cm x 15 cm to get maximum pollen for hybrid production. The design was Randomized Block Design (RBD) with 7 treatments and 3 replications. The plot size was 3m x 3m and the crop was raised during March to July 2020 (Virippu). A total of 96 and 128 plants were maintained in the main field of 9 m² plot size with 6:2 and 8:2 planting ratio respectively.

Techniques for hybrid rice seed production (Virmani and Sharma, 1993)

Chemical spraying

Spraying of GA₃ and brassinosteroid was done at 15-20% heading of tillers and 35-40% panicle emergence. The concentration of both chemicals is detailed in **Table 1**.

Supplementary pollination

Supplementary pollination was done with the help of rod driving. This operation was done 4-5 times (every 30 minute) between 9 am to 11.30 am.

Table 1. Concentration of GA₃ and brassinosteroid at different planting ratio

Treatment	Planting ratio	GA ₃ concentration (ppm)	Brassinosteroid concentration (ppm)
T ₁	6:2	50	2
T ₂	8:2	50	2
T ₃	6:2	50	6
T ₄	8:2	Control	Control
T ₅	6:2	70	2
T ₆	8:2	70	2
T ₇	6:2	Control	Control

Flag leaf clipping

Clipping of flag leaf was done when the primary tillers were at booting stage. It was practiced to enhance the pollen dispersal and to ensure higher seed set.

Roguing

To ensure high genetic purity, periodical roguing was done in the seed production plots during the maximum tillering stage, at flowering and just before harvesting.

Statistical Analysis

The biometric observation from seven treatments and three replications were taken and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were done by using statistical package GRAPES of Kerala Agricultural University.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Phenological studies in male sterile line (A-line)****Morphological and floral traits of CRMS 31A**

The performance of male sterile lines in terms of morphological and floral traits were studied as a preliminary approach for better understanding and improving the hybrid seed production. The knowledge on the vegetative and reproductive growth pattern of male sterile line is prerequisite for designing breeding programme; evaluation and characterization of cytoplasmic male sterile lines are important to determine their usefulness in hybrid development (Joshi *et al.*, 2000). Besides environmental factors, variations in floral characteristic of male sterile and pollen parents, plant height, length and angle of flag leaf, and panicle exertion affect natural outcrossing (Lin and Yuan, 1980). The important characters studied about sterile lines are described in **Table 2**.

The male sterile line, CRMS 31A started tillering at 23 days after transplanting. It showed the least response to fertilizer as compared to male parent; hence the number of tillers were reduced. The plant height was almost similar to that of male parent and; average height recorded was 123.23

Table 2. Morphological and floral traits of the male sterile line-CRMS 31A

Variables	Mean	SD	CV	Range
Tillering stage	23.30	1.34	0.06	21.00-25.00
Plant height at maturity (cm)	123.2	1.34	0.05	116.2-136.7
Total number of productive tillers	18.10	1.45	0.08	16.00-20.00
Total number of leaves	91.00	6.55	0.07	81.00-101.0
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	38.97	3.27	0.08	34.44-44.08
Days to panicle primordial initiation	58.90	2.13	0.04	56.00-63.00
Days to booting	66.20	4.16	0.06	55.00-70.00
Days to panicle emergence	74.10	1.79	0.02	72.00-77.00
Flag leaf angle (°)	15.60	2.63	0.17	12.00-20.00
Days to anthesis	85.50	2.27	0.03	83.00-89.00

cm with more productive tillers (18.10). Number of leaves produced by the main culm of CRMS 31 A was 91.0 with average flag leaf area 38.97 cm².

The panicle initiation was associated with the beginning of stem internodes and the developed panicle was microscopic in size (2-4 mm) with a fuzzed tip inside the main culm; and first panicle was observed on 58.9 days (**Fig. 1**). Later those panicles were developed completely inside and visible as minute panicle (**Fig.2**). The boot stage was initiated with the development of panicle primordial inside the culm. The increase in size of the panicle primordia and its upward extension through leaf sheath were detected rapidly with elongating culm. In Wide Abortive based CMS lines for 30-40% of the panicle remained inside the leaf sheath, thereby makes these spikelets unavailable for cross pollination (Joshi *et al.*, 2000). The booting stage started at an age of 67.2 day after planting. The first panicle emerged on 74.1 days old plant and fifty percentages of panicles emerged within a week. The flowering of CMS lines ranged from 81 to 88 days after sowing (Joshi *et al.*, 2000). The average flag leaf angle of CRMS 31 A was 15.6° which was very less when compared to traditional varieties. Small and horizontal flag leaf with good panicle exertion are very usefull in increased outcrossing (Lin and Yuan, 1980). The CRMS 31 A took 85.50 days to anthesis. That had taken 9 days to finish the anthesis of whole sterile spikelets on panicle (**Fig.3**). A positive correlation between duration of floret opening and percentage of sterility was described by Saran *et al.* (1971). Virmani (1996) reported that the A line had longer blooming period than B line.

Standardization of the dose of GA₃ and brassinosteroid for planting ratio of A, R line in the ratio of 6:2 and 8:2

The observations on seven morphological parameters were recorded at different growth stage and presented (**Table 4 & Fig 4**). The effect of different doses of

Fig. 1. Microscopic view of panicle initiation

Fig 2 Initiation and development of panicle primordial, in 58 days' old main tillers Fig 3. Microscopic view of a male sterile spikelet

GA₃ and brassinosteroids on sterile line recorded differential responses on biometric traits, along with planting ratio of A and R line enhanced number of hybrid seed set. From the study, the panicle exertion was improved than control. The combination of GA₃-70 ppm, brassinosteroid 2ppm with 6:2 planting ratio recorded maximum leaf angle (26°), panicle exertion (8.707cm), plant height (145.653 cm) and flag leaf angle (64.747 cm²). The same combination of GA₃ and brassinosteroid, with 8:2 ratio, increased the number of productive tillers (25.00), total tillers (27.00) and number of leaves (135.00). It might be due to the increased plant population. Increase in plant height by GA₃ application were reported by Gravino *et al.* (2009) in rice. Foliar application of gibberellic acid (GA₃) is an essential technique in promoting panicle exertion and obtaining high cross-pollinated seed set in hybrid rice seed production (Duan and Ma, 1992). Kumar *et al.* (2010) carried out an experiment in wheat and found that exogenous application of GA₃ increased the height of the plant and this increase was more profound with the increased concentration of GA₃ and it was also higher when compared with that of the control. Ramos *et al.* (2014) conducted a study to determine the optimum row ratio for male and female parents in hybrid rice and reported that 6:2 and 8:2 ratios were the best performers in all the three seasons. Application of GA₃ the growth of productive tillers was promoted at early and late growth stages through inhibition of unproductive tillers and production of heavy

panicles was increased thus resulting in increased yield (Liu *et al.*, 2012). Goufo *et al.* (2011) studied the effect of GA₃ in two aromatic rice cultivars namely Guixiangzhan and Peizaruanxiang and found that there is a significant increase in yield of the grain at both early and late growing seasons when compared with that of the control. Morinaka *et al.* (2006) observed that brassinosteroids play an important role in controlling seed size and weight, when applied externally in rice and it tends to increase seed yield per plant. In a pot culture experiment two forms of brassinosteroids BL (Brassinolide) and HBL (Homobrassinolide) at 5ppm and 1ppm respectively were used to study the effect of panicle exertion and found that the panicle exertion was improved resulting in enhanced cross pollination leading to higher seed set (Vivency, 1998)

The observations on five yield parameters were recorded at different growth stage and presented (Table 5 & Fig. 5). The treatment T₆ (GA₃-70 ppm, BRs-2ppm with 8:2 planting ratio) produced highest number of filled grains and high fertility percentage. The highest flag leaf angle (26.600°) was recorded in T₆ and it was on par with T₅ (Planting ratio of 6:2 with GA₃ 70ppm and BRs 2ppm) with flag leaf angle 26.400°. The minimum leaf angle was recorded for the control (6:2 planting ratio) treatment T₇ (12.267°) and it was on par with control (8:2 planting ratio) treatment T₄ (15.467°). The highest 1000 grain weight (19.400g) was recorded in the treatment T₃ (Planting ratio of 6:2 with GA₃ 50ppm and BRs 6ppm) followed by T₅ (Planting ratio of 6:2 with GA₃ 70ppm and BRs 2ppm) and T₆ (Planting ratio of 8:2 with GA₃ 70ppm and BRs 2ppm) with 1000 grain weight 17.267g and 16.500g respectively. The lowest 1000 grain weight was recorded in the treatments T₄ (13.733g) and T₇ (13.900g). The highest number of filled grains per panicle (33.00 nos) and lowest number of unfilled grains per panicle (17 nos) were observed in T₅ (GA₃-70 ppm, BRs-2ppm with 6:2 planting ratio). The control plants (T₄ and T₇) recorded the highest number of unfilled grains per panicle.

Vardhini and Rao (2005) conducted an experiment on the influence of brassinosteroids on germination, growth and yield parameter of sorghum and reported that brassinosteroids are highly effective in increasing the number of filled grains by inhibiting the number of unfilled grains. The spikelet fertility percentage was more in T₅ (19.507%), followed by T₃ (16.140%), and less fertility percentage was observed in control plants T₄ (7.127%) and T₇ (7.397%). Highest seed yield per plot (1489.320g) was recorded in T₆ (Planting ratio of 8:2 with GA₃ 70ppm and BRs 2ppm) followed by T₅ (1355.746g) lowest seed yield was observed in control plants T₄ (350.182g) and T₇ (316.757g). Emongor (2007) carried out a field experiment in two cowpea cultivars namely Blackeye and Tswana to evaluate the effect of GA₃ on growth

and development and reported that exogenous application of GA₃ increased the 1000 seed weight causing an increase in seed yield. Brassinosteroids play a vital role in regulating grain filling in rice, therefore application of brassinosteroids exogenously result in increase in 1000 seed weight (Chuan *et al.*, 2008).

Table 4. Morphological parameters recorded in the different treatments

Treatments	Leaf angle (°)	Panicle exertion (cm)	Plant height (cm)	Productive tiller	Total tiller	No. of leaves	Flag leaf area (cm ²)
T ₁	17.100	4.520	116.600	16.00	20.00	100.00	59.460
T ₂	17.600	5.473	117.093	17.00	21.00	106.00	55.143
T ₃	18.733	5.627	117.433	18.00	23.00	115.00	42.767
T ₄	15.467	16.447	111.007	11.00	18.00	88.000	35.683
T ₅	26.400	8.707	145.653	22.00	25.00	125.00	64.747
T ₆	26.600	8.233	144.160	25.00	27.00	135.00	60.307
T ₇	15.267	14.460	112.253	13.00	20.00	101.00	45.650
Mean	19.595	0.236	123.457	17.42	22.00	110.00	51.965
CD(0.05)	1.410	0.647	2.9360	1.153	2.188	10.939	9.2310
SE±(m)	0.457	0.210	0.9530	0.374	0.710	3.5500	2.9960
CV	4.043	153.99	1.3380	3.728	5.590	5.5900	9.9850

Fig 4. Comparison of morphological traits recorded in different treatments

CONCLUSION

The present investigation for standardization of GA₃ and brassinosteroid dosage at different row ratio in hybrid rice seed production revealed that the concentration of 70ppm GA₃, 2ppm brassinosteroid in 6: 2 planting ratio had highest morphological traits, spikelet fertility percentage, number of filled grains and lowest number of unfilled grains. Reduced yield per plot might be due to the decreased planting population in 6:2 ratio. The 50 ppm GA₃, 6ppm brassinosteroid in 6:2 planting ratio decreased flag leaf area, it might be due to the effect of BRs. Lack of panicle exertion

Table 5. Yield parameters in different treatments

Treatments	1000 grain weight (g)	Number of filled grains per panicle	Number of unfilled grains per panicle	Spikelet fertility percentage (%)	Seed yield per plot (g)
T ₁	14.963	22.00	169.00	11.653	647.299
T ₂	17.200	17.00	179.00	9.250	714.981
T ₃	19.400	28.00	175.00	16.140	961.779
T ₄	13.733	13.00	182.00	7.127	350.182
T ₅	17.267	33.00	170.00	19.507	1,355.74
T ₆	16.500	24.00	178.00	13.787	1,489.32
T ₇	13.900	13.00	183.00	7.397	316.757
Mean	16.137	21.428	176.571	12.123	833.723
CD (0.05)	2.625	3.162	N/A	2.100	153.290
SE±(m)	0.852	1.026	6.801	0.682	49.7420
CV	9.656	8.250	6.676	9.738	9.7870

and reduced seed filling are the main constraints in hybrid rice seed production in Kerala. The results showed that T₅ (70ppm GA₃, 2ppm brassinosteroid in 6: 2 planting ratio) had more promising effect on the hybrid rice seed production, hence this can be recommended for Kerala condition after trials over locations and seasons.

Fig 5. Comparison of yield traits recorded in different treatments

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